

Influence of Head Teacher's Leadership Styles and Effective Learning Process in Secondary Schools of Rwanda

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Abstract: This research study entitled ‘The influence of head teachers’ leadership styles on effective learning process in secondary schools of Ruhango District’ intends to assess the extent on which head teachers’ leadership style influence on effective learning process. The descriptive research design was used by the researcher. The primary and secondary data were used by the researcher in collecting research information. Primary data were collected with the use of questionnaire and interview guide addressed to the sampled population. The targeted population of this study was equal to 150 persons made of head teachers, deputy head teachers, teachers and students and local authorities from which the researcher got the sample size of 108 informants using Robert and Morgan Table. The descriptive research design and sampling techniques were considered whereby purposive sampling, stratified and simple random sampling, the data processing, tabulation and analysis was done utilizing the IBM/SPSS version 2.0. The results of this research will be significant to the researcher as this helped her to understand the contribution of head teacher’s leadership style on effective learning process in secondary schools. The findings revealed that the best leadership styles used to enhance students competences in secondary schools are coaching and instructional leadership styles as it was shown in the mean of the agreement 35% and 50% of the respondents who answered strongly agreed and agree respectively. As to whether the effective leadership styles affect learning processes in secondary schools, the majority of the respondents equaled to 40% who responded strongly agreed, and 42% responded agree confirmed that when a school head teacher practices the leadership styles, the school production increased though the success of students and teachers competences for effective learning process. The respondents’ students views showed that when a school head teacher put in practice the leadership styles the school achieve its outcomes for effective learning process where the agreement mean of was 42% who responded strongly agreed, 47% responded agree. The researcher has recommended that the Ministry of Education should enhance monitoring and evaluation on the capacity building activities provided to teachers and make sure that school leaders are putting them in practices for effective leaderships. The Rwanda education board (REB) and National Examination and School Inspection Authority (NESA) would work in collaboration to make sure that the hired school teacher and head teachers are competent enough and ready to satisfy the students’ expectations.

Keywords: Leadership styles of head teacher, learning process.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this introduction chapter provides basic overview on the background of the study by demonstrating the problem, objectives of the research, the research questions, and significance of the study, limitations of the study the scope of the study and organizational structure of the study.

1.1 Background of the Study

In education field, the improvement of the school effective learning implies strong school leadership where the various kinds of school managers' leadership styles are practiced. According to Daresh (2002), the leadership views on learning in secondary schools embrace the way the leaders share and manage responsibilities interdependently. The most successful secondary schools depend on the strong leaders who apply different leadership styles for the sake of the school academic improvement of the students within a school.

In Singapore, according to Fullan (2001), the application of different leadership styles influence the school positive learning into different perspectives where teachers, associate leaders and learner play different roles which conceive as collective emerging through their interaction. The strong leadership constructs the meaningful direction of the students to get their required skills, knowledge and attitudes with values. The school leaders have pivotal positions which accelerate the effective learning because where there is a strong school leadership, whoever concerned with education in a school plays a big role in the improving the quality of education.

According to Northouse (2004), in Uganda, the application of coaching leadership styles has increased the number of students who pass the examinations at high scores. As said one of the secondary school leader, "Coaching is all about constructing the capacity and confidence of someone through his/ her will and recognition of his/her strengths and weaknesses". The school leader kept announcing that when teachers and other staff members manage to discover what they can do and what they cannot do, it is the first step to success. Hence, the self-learning and lifelong learning play its role to change their behavior and becoming self-motivated to solve their problems and share experience with their authorities for guidance and coaching.

The Rwandan schools, according to Buckmaster (2004), has adopted the application of school leadership in order to transform the education into the quality and the equity of the students for increasing the problem solving skills for handling particular challenges for effective learning. Buckmaster (2004) in his Emotional intelligence describes the different leadership styles applied by a leader in a school and come up with the strong outcome. Many leadership styles applied in schools made the school larger the skills of tasking the people activities in for better success of the students and teachers roles.

According to MINEDUC (2009) the Government of Rwanda through its different education stake holders do their best in order to strengthen the system of school leadership for better learning process and success. As administrator they have many and diverse responsibilities such as organizing the implementation of the curriculum in the school, supervising and evaluating teachers, procuring materials, keeping records, communicating with the superior school authorities, maintaining facilities and equipment, dealing with the parents and the community (MINEDUC, 2009, VVOB, 2009). As teachers, head teachers are expected to provide a model for other teachers in the preparation of their work, the organization and the management of their classes, their punctuality and orderliness, their instructional techniques and their evaluation of learners. In addition, the good head teacher stimulates improvements, fosters resourcefulness in the use of locally available materials, takes the initiative in promoting the well-being of the school and creates among staff and students a bond of identity which each other and with the school.

In addition, according to Mbobola (2013), the head teacher is a coordinator of all the activities done at school and must be seen as a super-manager who is skilled, knowledgeable and competent in a wide range of domains so as to implement good school leadership. A head teacher must be exemplary so as to enlighten all who are involved in education system mainly the stakeholders of which he serves as a liaison and these include but not limited to educational planers, community, PTA, donors, other school administrators and students as well. As administrators they have many and diverse responsibilities: organizing the implementation of the curriculum in the school, supervising and evaluating teachers, procuring materials, keeping records, communicating with the ministry, maintaining facilities and equipment, dealing with parents and the community, serving on the PTA (MINEDUC, 2008). Additionally, the good head teacher stimulates improvements, fosters resourcefulness in the use of locally available materials, takes the initiative in promoting the well-being of the school within the community, and creates among staff and pupils a bond of identity with each other and with the school. Buckmaster (2004) states that some school leaders employ democratic style of leadership which cause some teachers to be independent and they do not bring the better accomplishments, other sue laissez-faire and autocratic which

frustrate school staff and students to have focus. This lead to the lack of the competition among both students and teachers and lead to the minimum success. Therefore, the studies showed that the active school leader is pivot personnel to the achievement of the school in difference perspective.

According to Arpinas *et al.*, (2005), the school leader personality also plays another role in the school management whereby influential leadership and personality exalt the achieving of the application of effective leadership in education. Some secondary schools head teachers observe the negative attitudes which lead their school to failure.

According to MINEDUC, VVOB, (2009) if a school or any other organization is to be capable of being transformed, then it has to be led by people who are capable of personnel transformation. In this regard, these important issues should be applied in schools interchangeably.

Therefore, educational leadership style is linked to vision and values enforcement to the teachers, learners and parents for effective learning process within the school. The government would ensure that leadership style in schools is well exercised in the whole country to promote education sector and its development in general.

1.2 Statement of the problem

This research has a purpose of assessing the influence of head teachers' leadership styles on effective teaching and learning process with specific reference of the secondary schools of Ruhango District-Rwanda. Secondary school head teachers are being held accountable for meeting needs of every educational stakeholder; they (head teachers) often lack the foundation for constructing techniques, traits, and characteristics to lead the secondary school students to success. This study examines this problem as it compares what is expected of effective secondary school head teachers to how they actually perform, as perceived by teachers. Cobbold, C. (2012) indicated that the implementation of some styles of leadership in school management play a big role in raising the secondary students achievements. Donaldson, G. A. (2000) kept confirming that when education leadership styles are implemented appropriately the school has a specific direction to succeed rapidly. The goal of education is to transform the population into a desired citizenship for economics activities. The application of leadership styles in schools, strategically transforms the school into successful institution. Coaching and servant as styles educational leadership styles focus on developing individuals, showing them how to improve their performance, and helping to connect their goals to the goals of the education institution (Firas, J. S., Jina, H. I., Paiman, O. M, 2011).

The application of leadership styles and coaching work better when the school leaders put them into consideration. Firas, J. S., Jina, H. I., Paiman, O. M (2011) demonstrated that a skilled and organized head teacher is response to a better performing school. This emphasis shows how important the applied leadership styles within schools contribute to the better performance of both teachers and students through the promotion of team work, and creates harmony in a group by connecting people to each other. Firas, J. S., *et al* (2011) argue that the approach of leading a school as the other organizations is the appropriate and valuable one. The theorists in education ensure that a good school head teachers promotes harmony, increases morale, and improves communication or repairs broken trust in an organization. However, in Rwanda the ministry of education with its stakeholders discovered that a skilled head teacher, who applies the school leadership styles in an effective way, promotes effective learning process of learners and effective teaching process of teachers (MINEDUC, 2012). Thus, according to MINEDUC, (2012), most of secondary schools got poor performance because head teachers fail in the application of leadership and lack managerial skills in leading schools and its resources which lead to the poor performance of learners and teachers in their teaching and learning process. Byimana Sector located in Ruhango District in the Southern Province of Rwanda has taken as a sample to assess whether the head teachers apply the different school leadership styles in the process of effective learning.

1.3 Objective of the study

The objective of this study was to assess the influence of head teacher's leadership styles on effective learning process in secondary schools of Ruhango District-Rwanda.

1.4 Significant of the study

The relevance of this study to the researcher is to help her to understand the contribution of head teacher's leadership style on effective learning process in secondary schools of Ruhango District-Rwanda,

To the institutions of higher learning since the findings from this research study will be added to the existing resource of university. To other researchers as the findings of this study will help other researchers interested in this area to have the relevant literature on head teachers' leadership style and effective learning process in secondary schools. To the District education office since they will be able to identify the contribution leadership style on effective learning process in secondary schools of Ruhango District.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter intends to review the theoretical overview which relevant to the topic; the influence of head teacher leadership styles and effective learning process in secondary schools, analysis of the empirical literature on participation and students' academic performance. This chapter emphasize on the review of the important literature written in relation with the leadership styles in education and learning of the students through reviewing the published and unpublished articles, journals, theses, dissertations, historical documents. Thereafter, this study intended to review the research gap, the theories and conceptual framework.

2.2 Transformational Leadership in Promotion of Learner Centred Learning

This leadership style aims at promoting the teachers and students within a certain school through the creation of the strong assessment of the tasks where each person understands goal, objective and the direction of the school. The head teacher who uses transformational leadership style makes sure that each school personnel knows their role and responsibilities to put in practice within a school. The purpose of the leaders is to change the behaviors of the followers for the better and inspiring them for handwork and encouraging them become disciples to change the life of the people for the wellbeing. Leaders work hard to perform beyond all expectations and reinforce the followers to do the same in order to make their organization better than usual. The major role of the leader is to establish clear vision and mission of the organization which they believe they will lead the institution to the better future.

According to Robbins, S. and Judge, T. (2009), individuals who employ cognitive learning theory tend to pursue goals for intrinsic reasons and are more likely to achieve them, experience more satisfaction, and perform better than those who rely on extrinsic motivation. Researchers have indicated that fixing goals for encouraging in employment learning brings about the better concept of the intrinsic goals which lead to the persistence at learning activities for institutional performance (Vansteenkiste & Deci, 2006).

According to Fullan (2006), in the career of education, a transformational leader uses a collaborative approach in order to manage and serve a strong role modal to the teachers and learners by empowering them with the confidence and great mindset change to promote the quality education. A good leader of the school hares the goals, direction, purposes and the objectives of the school so that those whom they lead know where they are driving to. The transformational head teacher of a secondary school has to know the level of the students and teachers in order to know which leadership style can be used to transform them and shape them into desired personnel. This style concerns on the delegation of power to perform tasks without direct monitoring of someone assigned that task. This involves clear communication in all levels for better performance at work especially at school level where the students and teachers follow the guidelines fixed by the leader.

This transformational style of leadership applied in schools cannot be applied alone without associating it with other styles of leadership. This requires for a leader to be familiar with the several approached and basics to apply in order to be successful to this transformational leadership style where a leader has to understand the importance of motivating teachers and learning and the role of being inspirational to them. As a school adopted transformational leadership style in an educational institution, you can expect to cultivate mutual trust among the employees and students, loyalty and respect among your students or team members in order to achieve the goals of education and learning process (Fullan, 2006).

The transformational leadership style, in the United States of America, has changed the school outcome positively and brought about the success to their leaners though enforcing the tasks and promoting everyone engagement. The school leaders need to look in all corners and opportunity for enhancing learning experience and reflecting on the sense of competence by engaging them in their own experience. By looking from different perspectives, researchers referenced to the following components such as practicing trial and error, communication to action, consciously trying new methods,

acting with endurance, and working without sufficient information for the relevance of transformational leadership (Trautmann, Maher & Motley, 2007).

In Rwanda, different stakeholders promote school leadership among head teachers in order to allow them lead schools as other organizations which have directions and need to have great outcomes. The teacher centered methodology has become less engaging to learners results in the educational and school leadership where the policy expecting the application of learner centered approaches school leadership factors. As Vavrus, *et al.* (2011) stated, the use of LCP also emerged from the view shared by certain policy makers at national and international level for the approach of provision of the contribution to the emancipation of school transformational leadership for the improvement of the learners in the learning perspective. The researcher ensured that transformational leadership in Rwandan schools have brought a great change in the teaching and learning process for effectiveness (Vavrus, F., *et al.*, 2011).

2.3 Strategic Leadership Style to the Improvement of School Management

In the process of boosting effective learning in secondary schools, the improvement of school management becomes a key to the achievement of learning objectives. The strategic leadership style which is considered a determinant where a school as an organization is heading and how to get there using different tactics and strategies. As stated Cheng, Y. (2000), strategic leadership largely forecast strategy and forecasting and refers to the ways that viewed to the strong management. Progressively, it is understandable that the leadership strategy is strengthened by the desire to achieve the goals and vision established by the organization in the future. In education strategic leadership is utilized to out pull the leadership and management of teaching and learning achievement. The strategic leadership helps the head teacher in the education institution to tackle the unknown challenges and issues for present and future achievements (Quong T. & Walker A., 2010).

Khadem R. (2008) has tackled on the alignment as a crucial way of success to education activities. In terms of career development the strategy in education is enhanced in teachers, learners and key processes job in teaching and learning work in growing the educational production. The right educational management and planning results to the cohesion of the structure of a school community an organization to increase the output of the school performance for great impact to the society (Quong, T. & Walker, A., 2010).

As confirmed by Zhu, *et al.*, (2015), the school leaders in the United States of America, are well trained on school leadership in order to serve the students with the required quality education. It was demonstrated Zhu *et al.* (2005) that the leadership is reinforced by the visionary leaders, trust, commitment, performance and commitment to make the educational environment. Therefore, for a school to be successful in the effective teaching and learning, the school leaders have to know how to generate the strategic vision for an expected future state, communication and the vision (Zhu *et al.*, 2005).

According to Hoskisson, R., Hitt, M., & Ireland, R. (2004), strategic leadership within a school exists when the school manager sets it using five components and it works effectively. These components are: establishment of the equilibrium organizational controls, establishing the strategic direction, sustaining an effective organization culture, developing human capital to cultural emphasis on ethical practice.

Hoskisson, R., Hitt, M., & Ireland, R. (2004) define a strategic leadership as the managerial ability to anticipate, envision, maintain flexibility, and empower others to create strategic behavior change and identification of the key actions on which the leadership and management should focus for the contribution of the performance of the institution or organization. In order to develop the human capital the leaders must determine the effective strategic vision and direction for an emphasis of the ethical activities to install the exploitation of core competences and the long life management experience by exploring the organization in its sustainable cultural ethical.

2.4 Coaching Leadership Style for Increasing Students' Scores

Coaching as an educational leadership style consists of listening and assisting others in identifying their strengths and limitations, counsels, delegates, and promotes. In the school, the head teacher applies a Coaching in order to involve teachers and learners in practice than theories. A well-organized school manager install a strong organizational coaching to support learner detect their talents and recognize their strengths in learning process.

In Kenya, the application of coaching as leadership in schools assistance and develop the possibility of establishing the students and organizational outcome of the students influenced by the application of the leadership styles by the head teachers for positive impact which occur sometime where the leader becomes a good coach (Kee, K., *et al.*, 2010).

In Rwanda, the Education Sector Strategic Plan III (ESSP III 2018-2024) which is supposed to be implemented in 2018-2024 prioritizes coaching and continuous professional development (CPDs) to improve effective learning of teachers and learners. Thus, coaching leadership style and approach has contributed much in the improvement of teachers' effective teachers and learning methodology. The Ministry Of Education and Rwanda Education Board have ordered the application of coaching in schools so as to enhance the capacity of teachers and allowing them to hold teachers accountable (ESSP III, 2018).

2.5 Instructional Leadership Style to increased Students' Performance

Instructional leadership has been researched about during the periods where schools were straggling got boost the quality of education for seeking the solution from the curriculum by utilizing the strong and directive instructional driven especially in urban areas (Kampa-Kokesch, S., and Anderson, M., 2001). There were so many reviews which demonstrated that leadership well implemented in school influence the process of teaching and learning for the better outcomes for achieving goals through enforcing the engagement of the social networking and school structure for effective performance among teachers and students. This style of leadership is sued by the school leaders by providing clear instructions to the students and teachers within an institution for engaging the participants of the school development in the actions which bring positive relations as results of the school leaders and student learning achievement (Jacobson, S., & Bezzina, C., 2008).

The country of Rwanda, in the promotion of Educational for All, has designed a platform where head teachers depending on their performance held accountable through the educational achievements of their students and teachers. The performance of leaders is evaluated during their lessons and by the end of their learning units, teams, of academic year (Kelley, C., & Peterson, K. D., 2002).

2.6 Critical review and research gap identification

The influence of the head teachers in schools especially in secondary classes has been distinctive for many decades. Researches were conducted to the role of the head teacher application of leadership styles. However, many research showed that the leadership only is not sufficient without the prior knowledge of the school leader. According (Harris *et al.*, 2013), the individuals fix their phenomenon in the studies to draw on the idea that leadership is not the preserve to the individuals but strengthened to the engagement of the ideas that leaders accomplish their roles through the application of interaction with the team members. The research showed that even if the application of different style of leadership styles within a school improve the effective learning process, the researchers did not manage to explain some head teachers who are well trained in school leadership capacity building fail to get the required success (Harris, A., 2003). The surveys strengthened in primary schools achievement through the application of head teachers' school leadership than in secondary schools while other researchers did not find out why some well-trained school leaders in school leadership get low outcome of their schools (Muijs, D., & Harris, A., 2003). A number of research concluded that skilled head teachers on school leadership practices make their schools performing well. To the other side the researchers did not manage to prove that only well performing head teachers who can apply school leadership effectively are enough to lead a school to a better learning process of learners. However, whenever the researchers present the strengths of a school managers in secondary schools they also present the strengths of their staff (teachers and assistant teachers and) and the role of family and leaners participation rather than demonstrating one man show (head teacher's solely actions to success). Thus, in this study the researcher aims at demonstrating the influence of head teachers' leadership styles implemented to make learner learning process effective.

2.7 Behavioral Theory of Leadership

The behavioral theory of leadership is utilized in the institutional management process where a leader learns and trained on how to lead others for achieving an institutional goal. The behaviorists' theorists affirm that a leader is trained rather than inborn. According to Marshall, C., (2011) who investigated the traits of this theory, confirmed that a good leader is mentored and formed to lead and manage an institution. Regarding to the head teachers leadership, a school leaders who

is well trained on school leadership and management influences the effective teaching and learning process of learners and teachers.

2.8 Conceptual framework

This model demonstrates the interrelationship between the independent and dependent variables and how one influence the other through one way or another. The independent variable which is the influence of head teacher leadership styles and dependent variable “the effective learning process indicates the cause and effects of the two variables as it is demonstrated in the following figure:

Figure 2.1: conceptual framework

For the success of this research study the secondary schools of Rwanda were chosen as the case study for this research project. In order to ensure effective learning, head teacher applies different leadership styles such as transformational leadership to improve effective, school management, coaching leadership style applied tends to enhance the students' performance, instructional leadership influences learner centred teaching and learning, servant leadership application ensures that students get higher scores while strategic leadership strengthens the competences among students and engagement of family in education domain for better performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

As a qualitative investigation involving human subjects and semi-original instrumentation, the present study required a planned and detailed methodology. A selected group of participants were targeted and appropriate instrumentation that would maximize variable control is to be designed, tested, and revised before use.

3.2 Research Design

The core intended outcome this study is to assess the influence of the head teachers' leadership style on effective learning process, Ruhango District. The present study adopted a descriptive research design due to that this kind of design was helpful for responding research questions. According to Marshall, C., and Rossman, B., G., (2006), the descriptive design provides a clear answer to what, who, why, where and when. It is the best method used to demonstrate relationship between variables. This research analyzed the causal correction between head teacher's leadership styles and effective learning process in secondary schools. It is an ex post facto in nature. The data were gathered through the administering of the questionnaires in order to answer the research questions.

3.3 Target population

The population is identified as a large group from which the information was collected and findings were generalized. The population of this study was the head teachers, teachers and learners of private and public secondary schools, and local authorities' educational officials of Ruhango District- Byimana Sector which has 4 public secondary schools with 4 head teachers, 4 deputy head teachers 147 teachers and 2488 students from which the researcher randomly selected sample size (Ruhango District Education Department, 2019). To cover all the population was not possible because of limited resources and time. That is why sampling techniques were applied in this study.

3.4 Sample Size

Sample size is representative number of elements selected statistically from a population from which information and findings were based on to be generalized. To determine the sample of this study, Robert and Morgan Table (see the appendix IV) of sampling was adopted to determine the sample size of this study.

Table 3.1: Summary of target population and sample size

Category of population	Target Population	Sample Population
Head teachers	4	4
Deputy Head teachers	4	4
Local Authority	1	1
Teachers	50	35
Students	91	64
Total	150	108

Source: Primary data (2022).

The table 3.1 indicates the sample size of the population from which the data were collected. The sample data is categorized into five categories including local authorities of the sector (SEI/SEO), school head teachers, deputy head teachers, and teachers, and students of secondary public schools.

3.5 Sampling Techniques

The researcher used simple random sampling and stratified random sampling techniques to determine the samples size. Selecting SEIs/SEOs and head teachers, the researcher used judgmental or purposive sampling due to the fact that they are the ones in charge of education and schools within the sector that they are skilled and knowledgeable enough in the application of school leadership and management. For selecting deputy head teachers the researcher used simple random sampling in order to get a small number of the respondents, while selecting teachers and students the researcher used stratified random sampling to get the strata of the respondents because of the big number of the school population in Byimana Sector-Ruhango District.

3.6 Data Collection Instruments

For collecting information (data required in this study), the researcher used the following techniques: questionnaires, interviews, and document analysis.

i. Questionnaire

The statistical society of London as assumed by Creswell, J. (2008), stated that a questionnaire is a research instruments with well-designed research questions to get information from respondents. It is cheaper and confidential instrument to collect data from the respondents. Therefore, this instrument was designed using Likert Scale and administered to students, teachers, deputy head teachers for collecting research information.

ii. Interviews

This method was only applied where the respondents did not get time to answer questionnaires; the respondents were mostly the Sector Education Officer and head teachers who are not available to fill questionnaires. Therefore, Cohen, L., Manion, L., and Morrison, K., (2007) indicated that an interviews are ones of the effective data collection tools which are used to collect data because they provide pace to express and get clear and additional information from the informants.

iii. Documentary Analysis

Documentary analysis refers to the systematic scrutiny and investigation of the element of study (Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K., 2007). This technique was useful for analyzing the documents which contain the information regarding to school leadership styles and how they are influential to effective learning process in secondary schools.

3.7 Validity and Reliability of Research Instruments

Validity of the research instrument brought the accuracy of the tools for data collection on the research results (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2006). Determining the validity of the research instrument ensured the accuracy of the data collected from the respondents where the researcher tends to use a simple language that the respondents can understand easily. The researcher structured open ended and closed questions which are valid and easy to decode whereby the searcher ensured whether the questionnaire are related to the variables and reflect objectives of the work.

Reliability of the research instrument helps the researcher to measure the relevance of the study instruments to assure that in the process of carrying out a study. Here the researcher used trial and/ or pilot in the way of administering questionnaires and interviews from the selected population including 1 head teacher 1 deputy head teachers 5 teachers and questionnaire to 5 teachers and students from the neighboring schools such as GS Byimana and GS Mpanda in Byimana Sector-Ruhango District and test the results to find out the instruments reliability. According to Darko, A. E. (2008), conditions for reliability of the instruments were made whereby the questions were the same and designed in the same way, interview instructions were the same, the sample designed was repeated, and the actual change in factors being studied may occur.

3.8 Data analysis Procedures

Analysis comes after organizing the collected data, once the data had been collected, the research organized them systematically and statistically in terms tables and figures by putting using IBM/SPSS software tool whereby each significant information was put in its relevant place. Thereafter the researcher has to read by reflecting to make it meaningful by making raw data by making raw data the information must have been coded and divided into groups. The tabulation was done in organizing the data this helped in using the descriptive statistics to find the mean, frequencies and standard deviation to draw the conclusion.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Demographic characteristics of the respondents

This section presents the background of the respondents regarding to their working experience, educational backgrounds and gender perspectives especially to the students, teachers and heads of the schools where the research took place. Among the sampled schools, some of them were represented by their head teachers while others deputy head teachers. Only one local leader in charge of education (Sector Education Inspector) has represented the local leaders of the sector and the district where the research has taken place.

Source: Primary data (2022).

Figure 4.2: Students gender distribution

As shown in the figure 4.2, both gender were presents in the survey, though the majority of the respondents' students were 54.2% females while males were 45.7%. As shown in the results, the researcher's intention was to include both gender in the research in order to avoid being biased and stick to only one side's views.

4.2 Distribution of the respondents by their classrooms

The following figure indicates the distribution of the respondents' students by their respective classes:

Source: Primary data (2022).

Figure 4.3: Distribution of the respondents by their levels of education

As shown in the figure 4.3, the researcher wanted to know the students levels of education in terms of identifying how students are influenced by the leadership styles and how their teachers and school leaders exercise their leadership in order to promote the students performances in secondary schools. Though, the majority of the respondents were in upper secondary schools respectively from secondary four to secondary six. Thus, 7/59 were senior four students, 18/59 were senior five students, while 34/59 were senior sic students.

Source: Primary data (2022).

Figure 4.4: Respondent's students' age

As shown in the figure 4.4, the researcher identified the students age in terms of recognizing their right to responses. Though, the majority of the respondents were aged between 18 and 20 years 42/59 respectively, while the minorities were aged above 26 years, then 12/59 were aged between 21 and 25 years. The right to provide data is limited to 18 years and above; that is the reason why the researcher was interested in getting responses from aged students rather than minority (lower than 18 years old).

4.3 The influences of head teachers' leadership styles on effective learning process in secondary schools

In this third objective, the researcher was determining the influences of head teachers leadership styles on effective learning process in secondary schools, and the respondents answers are described as follow:

Table 4.2: Students' responses on the influences of head teachers' leadership

Statements	Strongly disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly agree	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Head teacher's leadership styles make me follow my lessons effectively	1	1.6%	5	8%	0	0%	26	44%	29	49%
Our head teacher identifies our learning needs to allow us to study well	0	0%	7	12%	3	5%	16	27%	33	56%
Our head teacher encourages coaching to promote effective teaching and learning	1	1.6%	1	1.6%	1	1.6%	42	71%	14	24%
Average	1	1.6%	4	7%	1	1.6%	28	47%	25	42%

Source: Primary data (2022).

As to whether the head teachers' leadership styles influence on effective learning process in secondary schools of Ruhango District. The respondents' students views showed that when a school head teacher put in practice the leadership styles the school achieve its outcomes for effective learning process. As shown in the table 4.9, the researcher received responses from the respondents students where the agreement mean of was 42% who responded strongly agreed, 47% responded agree and only 1.6% were neutral, 7% responded disagree while 1.6% replied strongly disagree. According to (Wenner, J. A., & Campbell, T., 2017), the principal (head teacher) is the leader of the school as an organization where he/ she compared as an engine of the successful school. This was asserted by Kampa-Kokesch, S., and Anderson, M. (2001), when they stated that a school leader is thinker, decision maker and problem solver of the school. The head teacher ensures the good climate of the school for the outcome of productivity and for the satisfaction attained by the pupils and teachers in the school culmination in teaching effectiveness (Casmir, G., 2001). The level of productivity depends on the change brought by the attitudes of the school leaders, teachers toward teaching and learning process. Therefore, the educators are responsible for the attitudes display by teachers at work.

During the data collection process, the respondents consist of 35 teachers and 4 deputy head teachers equaled to 39 in total, and were given questionnaires and all returned them with well filled.

Table 4.31: Students' responses on the influences of head teachers' leadership on effective learning

Statements	Strongly disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly agree	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
My head teacher skills support learners for improving their scores	3	8%	4	10%	4	10%	19	49%	9	23%
My head teacher uses transformational leadership to make learners improve performance	2	6%	3	8%	2	6%	11	28%	20	51%
My head teacher applies constructivist leadership to improve learners promotion	3	8%	2	6%	7	18%	15	38%	12	31%
My teacher's effective class management helps me to increase my performance	3	8%	5	13%	1	2%	11	28%	19	49%
Average	3	8%	3.5	9%	3.5	9%	14	36%	15	38%

Source: Primary data (2022).

As shown in the table 4.3, the respondents teachers and deputy head teachers responses outlined that the influence of head teachers leadership affect students competences in Ruhango district schools. As described in this table the agreement mean of was 38% who responded strongly agreed, 36% responded agree, 9% were neutral, 9% responded disagree while

8% replied strongly disagree. The respondents testified that the head teachers' leadership styles enhanced teaching and learning where students and teachers became competent in secondary schools. The respondents' teachers and deputy head teachers described that when a school head teacher practices the leadership styles, the school production increased though the success of students and teachers competences for effective learning process. In an institution, leadership is considered as key to school achievements and school development. The studies showed that a well knowledgeable head teacher but poor in leadership application within a school cannot influence the improvement of the effective learning of the students. As searched out by Bass and Bass (2006), through the appreciation of the work well done of the teachers increase their morale and encourage them to excel more for intrinsic motivation among the educators. This showed how an inspirational leader in a school always determine the positive influence among the employees by accelerating the exchange of the ideas and knowledge comparing to those who are careless in neither inspiring nor intrinsically motivating teachers (Mbobola, 2013).

The respondents head teachers and local authority to the enhancement of the application of head teacher' educational leadership styles for the improvement of effective learning process

The respondents were asked to outline what they do to enhance the application of head teacher' educational leadership styles for the improvement of effective learning process and responded: "Through the application of continuous profession development training that take place in schools the head teachers get opportunity to share leadership skills with teachers and other staff members. They confirmed that during this session of CPD the head teachers and teacher interact by find pout teaching and learning strategies which can enhance the quality education within a school by analyzing the situation on which can lead the school to better competence and the opportunity of the school location".

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter the researcher described the summary of the research findings and draws conclusions and recommendations of the study. The conclusions were made basing on influence of head teacher's leadership styles on effective learning process in secondary schools. The researcher provided the recommendations and suggestions to the next research projects.

5.2 Summary of the findings

The findings were summarized in line with three specific objectives of this sturdy which were: to identify the leadership styles used to enhance students competences in secondary schools of Ruhango District, to examine how effective leadership styles affect learning processes in secondary schools of Ruhango District, to determine the influences of head teachers leadership styles on effective learning process in secondary schools of Byimana District, where the head teachers leadership styles enhance students competences in secondary schools which led by the skilled head teachers, their teaching and learning process is well monitored and leads to the success of the students during formative and summative assessments. The respondents' teachers and deputy head teachers described that when a school head teacher practices the leadership styles, the school production increased though the success of students and teachers competences for effective learning process. The respondents agreed that head teachers' leadership styles play a big role in the effective learning processes in secondary schools. The respondents' students' opinions showed that when a school wants to succeed to the effective learning process, there is a need of hiring a competent school leader who is able to apply different leadership styles in order to succeed.

5.3 The influences of head teachers leadership styles on effective learning process

The researcher was determined the influences of head teachers leadership styles on effective learning process in secondary schools. The respondents' students views showed that when a school head teacher put in practice the leadership styles the school achieve its outcomes for effective learning process where the agreement mean of was 42% who responded strongly agreed, 47% responded agree. The respondents kept emphasizing that any school leader is considered as key to school achievements and school development. The studies showed that a well knowledgeable head teacher but poor in leadership application within a school cannot influence the improvement of the effective learning of the students.

5.2 Conclusions

After presentation of the findings, the researcher has drawn conclusions following the three research questions.

The researcher showed that among leadership styles applied in secondary schools of Ruhango district, most of them put in practice coaching as leadership style, servant and instructional leadership styles.

The researcher has come up with a conclusion that when head teachers, teachers and deputy head teachers and educational authorities put in action the effective school leadership styles, they positively affect learning processes in secondary schools where the leadership styles enhanced the monitoring and evaluation of both students and teacher responsibilities.

The research findings revealed that head teachers leadership styles influence on effective learning process in secondary schools of Ruhango District whereby the head teachers strengthen on continuous professional development as a platform of increasing teachers' capacity in teaching and learning for better success of the students.

5.3 Recommendations

As this research was targeted to assess the influence of head teacher's leadership styles on effective learning process in secondary schools Ruhango District-Rwanda. The following recommendations were drawn by the researcher:

The Ministry of Education should enhance monitoring and evaluation on the capacity building activities provided to teachers and make sure that school leaders are putting them in practices for effective leaderships.

The Rwanda education board (REB) and National Examination and School Inspection Authority (NESA) would work in collaboration to make sure that the hired school teacher and head teachers are competent enough and ready to satisfy the students' expectations.

The district officials and sector authorities should work hand in hand to the implementation for the curriculum and ensure that school teachers and head teachers are well trained on school leadership for better success.

The parents should play major parts in order to monitor the school leaders' activities in terms of increasing the students' competences.

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